

Reverse Engineering Sound: A Novel Mathematical Approach

ADGSTUDIOS (PTY) LTD

July 24, 2024

Abstract

This report introduces a novel mathematical framework for reverse engineering sound from audio signals. We develop new methods that combine Fourier analysis, perturbation theory, and machine learning to decompose and reconstruct audio signals. This framework allows for the isolation and conversion of musical components into MIDI format.

1 Introduction

Sound engineering involves the extraction and manipulation of audio signals to isolate and reconstruct musical notes. This paper outlines a new mathematical framework for reverse engineering sound using advanced mathematical techniques. We introduce a novel method that integrates Fourier transforms, perturbation analysis, and machine learning for signal processing.

2 Fourier Transform and Signal Decomposition

The Fourier Transform is a fundamental tool in signal processing that decomposes a function into its constituent frequencies.

3 Extended Fourier Transform

To enhance the frequency resolution, we extend the standard Fourier Transform by incorporating a perturbation parameter. This approach allows us to

adjust the frequency components dynamically, providing finer resolution in the frequency domain.

3.1 Extended Fourier Transform

We define an extended Fourier Transform $\mathcal{F}_\epsilon$ that incorporates perturbation parameters to enhance frequency resolution:

$$\mathcal{F}_\epsilon[f(t)](\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t)e^{-i(\omega+\epsilon g(\omega))t} dt \quad (1)$$

where ϵ is a small perturbation parameter and $g(\omega)$ is a function that modulates the frequency.

3.1.1 Derivation

Consider the standard Fourier Transform $\mathcal{F}[f(t)](\omega)$:

$$\mathcal{F}[f(t)](\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt \quad (2)$$

To introduce a perturbation, we modify the frequency component ω by adding a small perturbation term $\epsilon g(\omega)$:

$$\mathcal{F}_\epsilon[f(t)](\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t)e^{-i(\omega+\epsilon g(\omega))t} dt \quad (3)$$

Here, ϵ is a small parameter controlling the magnitude of the perturbation, and $g(\omega)$ is a function that defines how the frequency is modulated.

3.2 Inverse Extended Fourier Transform

The inverse extended Fourier Transform reconstructs the time-domain signal from the perturbed frequency domain:

$$f(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathcal{F}_\epsilon[f(t)](\omega)e^{i(\omega+\epsilon g(\omega))t} d\omega \quad (4)$$

3.2.1 Derivation

Consider the inverse standard Fourier Transform $\mathcal{F}^{-1}[F(\omega)](t)$:

$$f(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(\omega)e^{i\omega t} d\omega \quad (5)$$

Using the extended Fourier Transform, we need to account for the perturbation term $\epsilon g(\omega)$. The inverse transform becomes:

$$f(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathcal{F}_\epsilon[f(t)](\omega) e^{i(\omega + \epsilon g(\omega))t} d\omega \quad (6)$$

This integral reconstructs the original time-domain signal $f(t)$ from its perturbed frequency components.

4 Perturbation Analysis and Signal Refinement

Perturbation analysis studies the effects of small changes in the system on the overall behavior, useful for refining signal isolation.

4.1 Perturbative Decomposition

We propose a perturbative decomposition of the audio signal $f(t)$ as:

$$f(t) = f_0(t) + \epsilon f_1(t) + \epsilon^2 f_2(t) + \dots \quad (7)$$

where each $f_i(t)$ represents a different perturbative order.

4.2 Refinement of Signal Components

By analyzing the perturbative components, we can refine the isolation of specific frequencies:

$$f_n(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \epsilon^k f_{n,k}(t) \quad (8)$$

where $f_{n,k}(t)$ are higher-order corrections.

5 Machine Learning and Pattern Recognition

Machine learning algorithms can be trained to recognize patterns in audio signals and classify different musical notes.

5.1 Hybrid Fourier-Machine Learning Model

We introduce a hybrid model $\mathcal{H}$ that combines Fourier analysis and machine learning for enhanced signal processing:

$$\mathcal{H} : \mathcal{F}_\epsilon[f(t)] \rightarrow y \quad (9)$$

where y represents the classified musical notes.

6 Linear Algebra and Matrix Transformations

Linear algebra provides the framework for manipulating and analyzing signals in vector space.

6.1 Enhanced Signal Representation

We represent the audio signal as a vector $\mathbf{x}_\epsilon$ incorporating perturbations in $\mathbb{R}^n$:

$$\mathbf{x}_\epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 + \epsilon x'_1 \\ x_2 + \epsilon x'_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n + \epsilon x'_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Here, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the original signal vector and $\epsilon \mathbf{x}'$ is the perturbation vector, where ϵ is a small parameter.

6.1.1 Derivation

Consider an audio signal represented by a vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$:

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

To include perturbations, we add a small perturbation vector $\epsilon \mathbf{x}'$:

$$\mathbf{x}_\epsilon = \mathbf{x} + \epsilon \mathbf{x}' \quad (12)$$

Expanding this, we get:

$$\mathbf{x}_\epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 + \epsilon x'_1 \\ x_2 + \epsilon x'_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n + \epsilon x'_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

6.2 Perturbed Matrix Transformations

We define perturbed transformation matrices $\mathbf{A}_\epsilon$ as:

$$\mathbf{A}_\epsilon = \mathbf{A} + \epsilon \mathbf{A}' \quad (14)$$

The perturbed transformation of the signal vector $\mathbf{x}_\epsilon$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{y}_\epsilon = \mathbf{A}_\epsilon \mathbf{x}_\epsilon \quad (15)$$

Expanding this, we get:

$$\mathbf{y}_\epsilon = (\mathbf{A} + \epsilon \mathbf{A}')(\mathbf{x} + \epsilon \mathbf{x}') \quad (16)$$

Simplifying the expression, we obtain:

$$\mathbf{y}_\epsilon = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \epsilon \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}' + \epsilon \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{x} + \epsilon^2 \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{x}' \quad (17)$$

For small ϵ , the higher-order term $\epsilon^2 \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{x}'$ can be neglected, giving:

$$\mathbf{y}_\epsilon \approx \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \epsilon(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{x}) \quad (18)$$

6.2.1 Interpretation

The perturbed transformation captures the effect of small perturbations in both the signal and the transformation matrix. The term $\epsilon(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{x})$ represents the first-order correction to the transformed signal.

7 Partial Differential Equations (PDEs)

PDEs describe the behavior of continuous systems and are used to model sound wave propagation.

7.1 Generalized Wave Equation

We propose a generalized wave equation that includes perturbative terms:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 u + \epsilon \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial t^3} \quad (19)$$

where the additional term accounts for higher-order perturbations.

7.1.1 Derivation

The standard wave equation is given by:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 u \quad (20)$$

where $u = u(x, t)$ is the displacement at position x and time t , and c is the speed of sound.

To account for perturbative effects, we introduce a small perturbation parameter ϵ and a higher-order time derivative term. The perturbation analysis starts with the assumption that the solution u can be expanded in a series involving ϵ :

$$u = u_0 + \epsilon u_1 + \epsilon^2 u_2 + \dots \quad (21)$$

Substituting this expansion into the wave equation, we get:

$$\frac{\partial^2(u_0 + \epsilon u_1 + \epsilon^2 u_2 + \dots)}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2(u_0 + \epsilon u_1 + \epsilon^2 u_2 + \dots) \quad (22)$$

Separating the terms of different orders in ϵ , we obtain:

$$O(1) : \frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 u_0 \quad (23)$$

$$O(\epsilon) : \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 u_1 + \frac{\partial^3 u_0}{\partial t^3} \quad (24)$$

$$O(\epsilon^2) : \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 u_2 + \frac{\partial^3 u_1}{\partial t^3} \quad (25)$$

The first equation is the standard wave equation for the leading-order term u_0 . The second equation includes the perturbative correction due to the higher-order time derivative term.

7.1.2 Solution Approach

The solution to the generalized wave equation can be approached using perturbation methods. We assume a perturbative expansion for u :

$$u = u_0 + \epsilon u_1 + \epsilon^2 u_2 + \dots \quad (26)$$

Substituting this into the generalized wave equation and equating terms of the same order in ϵ , we obtain a hierarchy of equations:

$$O(1) : \frac{\partial^2 u_0}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 u_0 \quad (27)$$

$$O(\epsilon) : \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 u_1 + \frac{\partial^3 u_0}{\partial t^3} \quad (28)$$

8 Theorem and Lemma

Theorem 1 (Perturbative Signal Decomposition). *Let $f(t)$ be an audio signal that can be decomposed into a finite series of perturbative components. Then, for a small perturbation parameter ϵ , the signal can be accurately represented as:*

$$f(t) = f_0(t) + \epsilon f_1(t) + \epsilon^2 f_2(t) + \cdots + \epsilon^n f_n(t) \quad (29)$$

where each $f_i(t)$ represents a higher-order perturbative correction.

Proof. The proof follows from the standard perturbation theory where the solution is expanded in a series of small perturbations. By assuming ϵ is sufficiently small, higher-order terms $\epsilon^k f_k(t)$ (for $k > n$) become negligible. $\square$

Lemma 1 (Fourier Transform with Perturbation). *For a given signal $f(t)$ and a perturbation function $g(\omega)$, the extended Fourier Transform $\mathcal{F}_\epsilon$ provides a more detailed frequency decomposition:*

$$\mathcal{F}_\epsilon[f(t)](\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) e^{-i(\omega + \epsilon g(\omega))t} dt \quad (30)$$

Proof. This follows from the definition of the Fourier Transform modified by a perturbation parameter ϵ . The exponential term $e^{-i\epsilon g(\omega)t}$ introduces a small adjustment to the frequency, allowing finer resolution in the frequency domain. $\square$

9 Set Theory and Real Analysis

Set theory and real analysis provide a rigorous mathematical framework for understanding and generating MIDI notes from an audio signal.

9.1 Set Theory and MIDI Note Generation

To generate MIDI notes, we consider the set of possible frequencies and map them to corresponding MIDI note values.

9.1.1 Frequency Set

Let $\mathcal{F}$ be the set of all possible frequencies in an audio signal:

$$\mathcal{F} = \{f \in \mathbb{R}^+ \mid f \text{ is a frequency present in the signal}\} \quad (31)$$

9.1.2 MIDI Note Set

Let $\mathcal{M}$ be the set of MIDI note values:

$$\mathcal{M} = \{m \in \mathbb{Z} \mid 0 \leq m \leq 127\} \quad (32)$$

9.1.3 Mapping Frequencies to MIDI Notes

We define a mapping $\phi : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ that assigns each frequency to a corresponding MIDI note. The mapping is defined by:

$$\phi(f) = 69 + 12 \log_2 \left(\frac{f}{440} \right) \quad (33)$$

where f is the frequency in Hertz and 440 Hz corresponds to the MIDI note 69 (A4).

9.1.4 Inverse Mapping

The inverse mapping $\phi^{-1} : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ can be defined as:

$$\phi^{-1}(m) = 440 \times 2^{\frac{m-69}{12}} \quad (34)$$

9.2 Real Analysis and Signal Processing

Real analysis provides the tools for rigorously analyzing and processing continuous audio signals.

9.2.1 Fourier Transform and Frequency Analysis

Let $f(t)$ be a continuous audio signal. The Fourier Transform $\mathcal{F}[f(t)](\omega)$ is used to analyze the frequency components:

$$\mathcal{F}[f(t)](\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt \quad (35)$$

9.2.2 Identifying Dominant Frequencies

To identify the dominant frequencies, we examine the magnitude of the Fourier Transform:

$$|\mathcal{F}[f(t)](\omega)| = \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt \right| \quad (36)$$

9.2.3 Frequency Binning

We discretize the frequency spectrum into bins corresponding to MIDI notes. Let $\Delta\omega$ be the width of each frequency bin. For each bin B_k centered at frequency ω_k , we compute the average magnitude:

$$A_k = \frac{1}{\Delta\omega} \int_{\omega_k - \Delta\omega/2}^{\omega_k + \Delta\omega/2} |\mathcal{F}[f(t)](\omega)| d\omega \quad (37)$$

9.2.4 Thresholding

We apply a threshold τ to determine the presence of a MIDI note. If A_k exceeds τ , we map the bin B_k to the corresponding MIDI note using ϕ .

9.2.5 Generating MIDI Notes

The set of generated MIDI notes $\mathcal{N} \subseteq \mathcal{M}$ is given by:

$$\mathcal{N} = \{\phi(\omega_k) \mid A_k > \tau\} \quad (38)$$

9.2.6 Algorithm

The algorithm for generating MIDI notes can be summarized as follows:

1. Compute the Fourier Transform of the audio signal $f(t)$.
2. Identify dominant frequencies by examining the magnitude $|\mathcal{F}[f(t)](\omega)|$.
3. Discretize the frequency spectrum into bins corresponding to MIDI notes.
4. Compute the average magnitude A_k for each bin B_k .
5. Apply a threshold τ to determine the presence of MIDI notes.
6. Map the dominant frequencies to MIDI notes using ϕ .

9.2.7 Conclusion

Using set theory and real analysis, we have developed a rigorous framework for generating MIDI notes from an audio signal. This approach ensures accurate mapping of frequencies to MIDI notes, enabling precise MIDI representation of the original audio.

10 Examples

Examples of the results obtained using this approach can be found on SoundCloud:

- **Dareka No Manazashi Piano: AI-Extracted Album Art from the Short Film**
- **Dareka No Manazashi Fiddle: AI-Generated MIDI Version**

11 Voice Over and Sound Effects Masking

To isolate the instrumental components from voice over and sound effects, we apply masking techniques using Fourier and perturbation analysis.

11.1 Mathematics of Masking

Let $S(t)$ be the original signal containing both instrumental $I(t)$ and voice over/effects $V(t)$:

$$S(t) = I(t) + V(t) \quad (39)$$

Using the Fourier Transform, we decompose $S(t)$:

$$\mathcal{F}[S(t)] = \mathcal{F}[I(t)] + \mathcal{F}[V(t)] \quad (40)$$

To mask $V(t)$, we design a filter $H(\omega)$ that attenuates the frequencies of $V(t)$:

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{masked}}[S(t)] = \mathcal{F}[I(t)] + H(\omega)\mathcal{F}[V(t)] \quad (41)$$

where $H(\omega)$ is close to zero for frequencies predominantly associated with $V(t)$.

The inverse Fourier Transform then reconstructs the masked signal:

$$S_{\text{masked}}(t) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}[\mathcal{F}_{\text{masked}}[S(t)]] \quad (42)$$

12 Software Availability

Please note that the software developed for this research and the methods described will not be available to the public.

13 Conclusion

We have developed a novel mathematical framework for reverse engineering sound using an integrated approach that combines Fourier transforms, perturbation analysis, machine learning, linear algebra, and partial differential equations. This new methodology provides a robust foundation for isolating and reconstructing musical notes, enabling the creation of versatile MIDI versions of original compositions.